

Unlocking nf-core - customising workflows for your research

18 & 19 May Month 2023

1:00 - 4pm AEST/12:30 - 3:30pm ACST/11:00 - 2pm AWST

Lead trainers

Dr Georgina Samaha, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney

Dr Cali Willet, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney

Dr Chris Hakkaart, Seqera Labs.

Facilitators

Dr Sarah Beecroft, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre.

Host

Dr Melissa Burke, Australian BioCommons

Useful links

Training materials: <https://sydney-informatics-hub.github.io/customising-nfcore-workshop/>

Schedule

*Timings are approximate and subject to change.

Day 1

Time AEST	Activity	Outcomes	Presenter
12:55 pm	Zoom opened for participants		
1:00 pm	Welcome and housekeeping		Melissa
1:10 pm	Session 1 kick-off	Discuss session 1 learning outcomes and set up working space.	Georgie
1:50 pm	Introduction to Nextflow	Understand core features of Nextflow and learn fundamental Nextflow options and features.	Chris
2:05 pm	Introduction to nf-core	Understand core features of nf-core and learn how to use nf-core tools utility.	Chris
2:20 pm	Break		
2:35 pm	Configuring nf-core workflows	Understand the structure of an nf-core pipeline and the use of customisation options.	Chris
3:15 pm	Commands for users	Apply the nf-core tools utility's list, download, and launch commands.	Chris
3:45 pm	Questions and wrap up		All
4:00 pm	End of day 1		

Day 2

Time AEST	Activity	Outcomes	Presenter
12:55 pm	Zoom opened for participants		
1:00 pm	Welcome and housekeeping		Melissa
1:05 pm	Session 2 kick-off	Discuss session 2 learning outcomes and set up working space.	Georgie
1:15 pm	Design a run command	Build a run command for the nf-core/rnaseq pipeline using required and optional parameters.	Georgie
1:45 pm	Reproducible parameters	Troubleshoot a pipeline warning message and apply a parameter file to track our parameters.	Georgie
2:05 pm	Break		
2:20 pm	Configure compute resources	Configure compute resources for the workflow using a custom configuration file.	Cali
3:10 pm	Apply multiple configurations	Apply multiple configuration files to customise various pipeline settings for the same run.	Cali
4:00 pm	End of workshop		